

FEATURES OF TEACHING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS THE TECHNIQUE OF SPRINTING

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of increasing the level of general physical, speed-strength and technical readiness of university students, the application of methods for improving the technique of sprinting at all stages of the educational process during the entire period of study. Attention is paid to technical exercises to correct shortcomings in running, based on physical capabilities. The process of overcoming a short distance is analyzed in stages: start, starting acceleration, passing the distance and finishing. Recommendations are given for improving the technique of sprinting.

Key words: sprinting, running exercises, start, finish, turn running, short distances, sprint.

Introduction. The process of physical education in universities is implemented in accordance with the state educational standards of higher professional education, which impose requirements on the mandatory minimum content and the level of bachelors in the discipline "Physical Education". Students experience significant difficulties in fulfilling the standards in the 100-meter run [1, 2].

Sports results in sprinting largely depend on mastering the rational running technique. The process of training and improvement of sports technique takes place in all courses of study at the university, but the irrationality of the method of initial training in the technique of sprinting hinders the overall growth of achievements in the sprint [3, 4, 5].

Running is the simplest, most accessible and physiological sport. It would seem that it could be easier - put on a sports uniform, sneakers, go to the park or the stadium and run to your health. However, such a simple approach often turns into overwork, injury and frustration for beginners [9].

For productive classes, not only the right equipment is necessary, but also some technical preparedness. Thus, the running technique, the correct calculation of the intensity of training, the frequency of classes, proper nutrition and even shoes are of great importance [5, 7].

Short distance sprinting - running at maximum speed for a short distance. This species is good for the development of physical data. Can be combined in training as an interval: sprinting - easy running - footing.

Short-distance running, or sprint, is carried out on segments lasting from 60 to 400 meters [1, 6, 8]. This discipline requires excellent coordination and high speed abilities. Sprinting is a short-distance run, not only in a straight line, but also in a turn. Running along a turn has a number of features, therefore, in the technique of running along a distance, a separate phase is distinguished: running along a turn [11, 13, 14].

The whole process of overcoming a short distance can be divided into 4 stages: start, starting acceleration, passing the distance and finishing. For such segments, a low start is considered the most convenient [9, 14]. It allows you to give the runner the necessary acceleration, to accelerate in the first meters to the maximum possible speed. The main thing is to push off correctly and energetically at an acute angle to the treadmill and to perform movements with your arms and legs as quickly as possible when leaving the start. Each phase has its own motor task. At the start, it is necessary to take such a starting position that will allow the athlete to start running as soon as possible, the starting acceleration is dedicated to gaining speed, distance running is to maintain distance speed, and finishing is to resist its loss [16].

The growth of results in sprinting depends on all aspects of the athlete's preparedness (technical, physical, psychological). Running technique is the main direction in the training of sprinters [12]. Technique in sports is the way in which an exercise is performed. This is not only the form of movement (direction, amplitude, pace), but also its quality, essence - alternation of efforts, change of speed, rhythm, that is, everything that follows from the interaction of internal and external forces. When choosing one or another method of performing an athletics exercise, in addition to the requirements imposed by the rules of the competition, the main criteria are efficiency, economy, and simplicity of this method.

Sprinting is an anaerobic exercise. Due to the extremely high intensity, ATP - creatine - becomes the main source of energy, and not glucose or fat, as is the case in other types of running.

Smooth running promotes the development of speed, strength, has a positive effect on muscle growth, strengthens the heart and lungs, and has a good effect on overall health. Sprinting is an effective way to stimulate fat loss, and due to the nature of the load, smooth running has little effect on muscle mass burning, moreover, it promotes muscle building, especially the skeletal muscles of the lower body.

The main task of a sprinter is to gain speed as quickly as possible and maintain it for as long as possible. According to studies, the maximum possible running speed for a given person is reached at the sixth second, and after the eighth second it begins to decrease. Despite the fact that in general the sprint technique is individual, some rules of technique can be distinguished.

The main means for the formation of a speed constant are multiple runs at low and medium speeds at various distance segments (60-100 m): special running exercises at segments of 30-40 m - running with a high hip lift, mincing run, running with a throwing of the lower leg, running jumping steps. Exercises are performed freely, with a gradually increasing frequency of movements, followed by a transition to normal running. Repeating these exercises many times in each

session leads to the elimination of typical mistakes in running technique: insufficient hip elevation, incomplete leg extension during repulsion, excessive inclination or deviation of the body, keeping the elbows away from the body.

The main exercises for teaching the technique of running in a turn is running 50-80 m with acceleration at the turn of the treadmill. First, training takes place at the extreme (6 - 8) tracks, then 1-2; running at different speeds in a circle with a radius of 20-10 m; running with acceleration in a straight line with access to a turn; running with acceleration in a turn and exit from a turn to a straight line; imitation of hand movements. As you master the technique of running for short distances along a track of a larger radius, you should move on to running along a track of a smaller radius.

Let's analyze the initial phase, the start. The sprint is most typical for a low start, thanks to which the speed is most effectively gained at the start of the race. An effective start is made by the starting machine and blocks, with their help the runner receives support for the start, the most comfortable position of the legs and their angle of inclination. So there are several types of installation of support blocks: With the criterion of a normal start, the near support is placed over 1.5 feet from the start, and the far one is at least 2 feet from the near one; In conditions of a stretched start, the distance from support to support is 1 foot, and to the line is not less than 2 feet; In conditions of a close start, the distance from support to support remains the same as in the previous version, and the distance to the line is set at 1,5 feet. After voicing the command to start! the athlete takes his place in front of the supports, bends over and places his hands behind the starting line. After that, you should rest your feet on the pads so that your socks rest on the canvas of the running road. With the back foot, you need to kneel and bring your hands in front of the start line. After the sign of attention, it is necessary to straighten the legs, tear off the knee from the track. Raise the pelvis, but try not to overexert your arms.

The second phase is picking up speed, which is worth paying attention to. This is one of the most important phases as it sets the speed and timing of the run. If you make a mistake in it, then this will directly affect the result. Most importantly, after the start, it is necessary to straighten the front leg while remaining torso in the slope, after which it is accompanied by raising the hip of the back leg, and the next step is taken. It is important to note that the tilt of the body must be gradually reduced during acceleration and by the 15th step, completely switch to the standard one. With the development of maximum speed, the torso must be positioned slightly at an inclination forward. Feet must land on the front of the foot. It is also worth noting that many runners have a main leg, this should be eliminated by additional training on the non-main leg. Hands must be kept in a bent position and displays crosswise with legs.

Having accelerated at the start, it is necessary to keep the speed until the very finish; The 200 meter distance is different in that it will still be necessary to run a turn. To do this, you need to run the distance to the turn a little slower than the maximum result. In turn, the torso should be tilted to the left; The 400-meter distance is overcome as follows: 1/4 of the distance is the maximum acceleration, and after a gradual decrease in speed.

Conclusions. Runners, based on their physical capabilities, are selected technical exercises to correct shortcomings in running. A beginner should perform separate exercises for technique, this is necessary for the formation of correct execution.

Sprinting - occupies a significant place in the program of physical education in higher educational institutions, as one of the main types of athletics, as a means of training, it helps to increase the level of achievement in most other sports. The technique of sprinting is purely individual and, despite certain biomechanical characteristics, depends on the specific individual characteristics of the athlete, as well as on the levels of power and speed achieved by him. This, of course, does not

exclude the common elements of technology common to all rational elements, the improvement of which they are engaged in to this day.

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